

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE POLYETHER-ETHER KETONE (PEEK)

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue crack growth behavior of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite polyether-ether ketone(PEEK) has been studied in room temperature ambient atmosphere. The investigation also examined the influence of load ratio (R) on the fatigue crack growth rate and the fatigue threshold. The crack growth mechanism in fatigue in this material was also determined by detailed fractographic analysis of the fracture surfaces.

INTRODUCTION

Failure under cyclic or repeated loading, fatigue, continues to be a very serious problem for structural components. The useful life of a structural component subjected to cyclic loading or fatigue is determined primarily by the time required for the cracks or flaws already present in these structures to grow from subcritical dimensions to the critical size. At the critical flaw size the failure of the component will take place. The critical flaw size under a given loading condition is determined by the plane strain fracture toughness [1] of the material.

The fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN , has been related to the stress intensity range ΔK and the Paris equation [2] has been found extremely useful for characterizing the fatigue crack growth rate. The Paris equation relates the crack growth rate, da/dN , with stress intensity range ΔK in the form of a Power law,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C.(\Delta K)^m \quad (1)$$

Here C and m are material constants and ΔK is the difference between maximum and minimum stress intensity factors. The Paris equation [2] can be used to determine the total fatigue life of a structural component by the integrating from the initial flaw size (a_i) to the final crack length (a_f) or the critical flaw size:

$$\int_{a_i}^{a_f} \frac{da}{(\Delta K)^m} = \int_0^{N_f} dN \quad (2)$$

$$\therefore N_f = \int_{a_i}^{a_f} \frac{da}{(\Delta\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}Y)^m} = \int_{a_i}^{a_f} \frac{da}{(\Delta\sigma)^m \pi^{m/2} a^{m/2} Y^m}$$

where N_f = total number of cycles for failure ,

$\Delta K = \Delta\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}Y$ and $\Delta\sigma$ = stress range = $\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}$ in fatigue cycle, and,

Y = geometric factor. (Here σ_{\max} is the maximum stress, and σ_{\min} is the minimum stress in a fatigue cycle)

Fatigue threshold, ΔK_{th} , is another extremely important parameter for structural design. The fatigue threshold defines the stress intensity range below which pre-existing cracks or flaws present in a structural component will not propagate. Hence, both fatigue crack growth rate and fatigue threshold data are needed for failure safe design practices for structural components in cyclic loading situations.

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite polyether-ether ketone(PEEK) is a new and emerging material which is finding increasing applications in aircraft as well as automotive industries. PEEK is a high temperature resistant thermoplastic polymer. Being a thermoplastic polymer, it has more toughness and has better fatigue and fracture resistance than most thermoset polymers. This makes it an ideal material for applications in critical structural components in automotive applications. Fatigue crack growth rate and fatigue threshold data of this material is extremely important and needed for failure safe design practice as well as for the development of this material for automotive and aircraft applications. However, very little information is currently available about the fatigue threshold and fatigue crack growth behavior of PEEK.

Depending upon maximum stress level, fiber type and matrix, fatigue damage in composite is dominated either by fiber breakage or by matrix micro-cracking. Unlike metals, fiber reinforced composites seldom fail along a self similar and well defined crack plane. Instead, fatigue damage in fiber reinforced composites occurs at multiple locations in the form of fiber breakage, delamination, debonding and matrix cracking or yielding. Mechanism of fatigue failure in PEEK based composite is not yet known. A detail understanding of the crack growth mechanism in these materials is also needed for development of these materials for structural applications and to improve fatigue crack growth resistance and fracture toughness.

The primary objective of this investigation was to characterize the fatigue crack growth behavior of this material at room temperature in ambient atmosphere. The secondary objective of this study was to examine the influence of load ratio (R) on fatigue crack growth rate and fatigue threshold of this material. The final objective of this investigation was to determine the crack growth mechanism in fatigue by detail fractographic analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material:

The material used in the present investigation is a composite made of short, randomly oriented carbon fibers reinforced in polyether-ether ketone (PEEK). The material was molded in sheet form from which the compact tension (CT) specimens were prepared as per ASTM Standard E-647[3]. A schematic of the compact tension specimens used in this study is shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were examined with X-rays for any detectable void or flaws present in the specimens before carrying out fatigue threshold testing.

Fatigue Threshold Testing:

The compact tension specimens were polished to remove the film of releasing agent and any shine that creates problem in detecting the crack accurately during fatigue testing. The specimens were initially precracked in fatigue to produce a 2mm-long sharp crack in accordance with ASTM Standard E-647[3]. Precracking was carried out at a ΔK level of 4.5 MPa \sqrt{m} . After fatigue precracking, fatigue testing was carried out using a servohydraulic MTS (Material Test System) test machine. All tests were carried out in room temperature, ambient atmosphere and in load-control mode. A constant amplitude sinusoidal wave form was applied. Tests were carried out at three different load ratios, $R = 0.00, 0.10, 0.30$ respectively. The crack lengths and the number of cycles for crack propagation were continuously recorded. The crack lengths were monitored continuously with the help of an optical traveling microscope.

The fatigue threshold was determined using the load shedding technique as per ASTM Standard E-647[3]. This procedure involves slowly decreasing the load values and recording the crack growth rate. This load reduction was done only upto a maximum of 5% and that also only after the crack had grown by at least 1mm at the previous ΔK level. In this way any overload retardation effect caused by prior ΔK was avoided. The threshold was determined graphically from the plot of $\log da/dN$ versus $\log \Delta K$. The threshold was identified as the value of ΔK at which the crack growth rate was of the order of 10^{-10} m/cycle in accordance with ASTM Standard E-647[3]. Three to four identical test specimens were tested for each load ratio. The average values from these specimens were then taken as the representative of crack growth rate data and the fatigue threshold.

Fractographic samples were prepared by cutting specimens from the fracture surfaces. The fracture surface of the specimens were examined under a scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 2, 3, and 4 report the fatigue crack growth behavior of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK at three different load ratios. The Paris constants C and m of the material at all these load ratios are reported in table 1. The fatigue threshold data of the material at all these load ratios are also reported in table 1.

In figure 5, the fatigue crack growth behavior of the material are compared at the three different load ratios. This figure shows that the crack growth rate of PEEK increases as the load ratio increases. In the threshold region the difference in crack growth rates are significant. However in the linear or high ΔK region the difference in crack growth rates at different load ratios gradually diminishes. Or in other words, load ratio has most significant influence on crack growth rate in the threshold region.

FIGURE 1: Compact Tension Specimen
All Dimensions in inches

Figure 2: Fatigue crack growth behavior of Carbon fiber reinforced PEEK

Figure 3: Fatigue crack growth behavior of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK

Figure 4: Fatigue crack growth behavior of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK

Table 1

Fatigue Threshold and Paris's Constants

Load Ratio (R)	Fatigue Threshold ΔK_{th} (MPa \sqrt{m})	Paris's Constant C	Paris's Exponent 'm'
0.0	3.63	2.3×10^{-19}	16
0.1	3.40	6.3×10^{-20}	16.6
0.3	2.85	6.5×10^{-22}	23

Test results reported in table 1 show that as the load ratio increases, the threshold value decreases. In figure 6 the threshold is plotted against load ratio R. It appears that there is a linear relationship between load ratio and fatigue threshold in this material.

Several researchers[4-6] have examined the influence of load ratio on fatigue crack growth behavior in various materials. In most cases, the crack growth rate increases with increase in load ratio. This increase in crack growth rate with increase in load ratio has been attributed to the crack closure [7] effect. It is well known that cyclic plasticity behind a propagating crack can cause partial closure of the crack surfaces. This crack closure in turn reduces the effective stress intensity factor $\Delta K_{eff} = K_{max} - K_{op}$. Similar phenomenon appears to be taking place in this material also. At higher load ratio (R=0.3) crack is always open therefore the effective stress intensity factor is higher than in case of lower load ratio (R=0 or 0.1). This higher ΔK_{eff} is responsible for the higher crack growth rate at higher load ratio and consequently for lower fatigue threshold at higher load ratio.

Many researchers [8-10] have studied the influence of load ratio on fatigue crack growth rate and fatigue threshold in a wide variety of materials. Vosikovsky[8] analyzed the data from literature and observed that in most cases a linear relationship exists between load ratio and fatigue threshold. He proposed an empirical relationship of the nature $\Delta K_{th} = \Delta K_{th0}(1 - bR)$ where ΔK_{th0} is the value of threshold at the load ratio R = 0, and b is a material parameter. Barsom [9] also reported a linear relationship of the nature $\Delta K_{th} = \Delta K_{th0} - BR$ where B is again a material parameter. Klensil and Lucas [10], on the other hand, observed a power law relationship of the nature $\Delta K_{th} = \Delta K_{th0}(1 - R)^\gamma$ where γ is a material and environment dependent parameter. Our test results show a linear relationship between ΔK_{th} and R and indicate that Barsom's relationship can characterize the relation between load ratio (R) and fatigue threshold in PEEK, most appropriately.

In figure 7, the Paris constants C is plotted against the load ratio R for the material. Figure 8 on the other hand is a plot of Paris exponent 'm' against the load ratio 'R'. Both of these figure show a linear relationship between C and R as well as 'm' and R. It is interesting to note that while Paris constant C increases with load ratio R, the Paris exponent 'm' on the other hand decreases with R. In figure 9 the Paris constant C is plotted against the Paris exponent m in the form of log C versus m. This figure shows that a linear relationship exists between log C and m in this material. Similar relationship between log C and m have been reported in wide variety of materials[11-13]. Our test results also show that there exists a linear relationship between log C and m or in other words it is possible to calculate one constant from the other and vice versa.

The fractographs of the material at low, medium and high ΔK range are shown in figures 10, 11, and 12 respectively. The fractograph show that there is increasing roughness of the

Figure 5: Effect of load ratio on fatigue crack growth behavior of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK

Figure 6: Influence of load ratio on fatigue threshold of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK

Figure 7: Influence of load ratio on Paris's constant 'C'

Figure 8: Influence of load ratio on Paris's exponent 'm'

Figure 9: Relation between Paris's constant C and m

Figure 10: Fractograph of the material in low

ΔK region

Figure 11: Fractograph of the material in linear region

Figure 12: Fractograph of the material in high ΔK region

fracture surfaces as the ΔK value of the material increases. Furthermore, no significant difference in crack growth mechanism was found at similar ΔK levels in different load ratio specimens, or in other words at the same ΔK , the higher or lower load ratio did not affect the crack growth mechanism. The fractographs at very high ΔK region show fiber breakage as well as the delamination at the fiber matrix interfaces in this material. Comparing the current test results[14] with the crack growth rate data of PEEK (without carbon fiber reinforcement) it become obvious that there has been significant improvement in fatigue crack growth resistance of PEEK with carbon fiber reinforcement. This is partly due to increase in specimen stiffness and additional energy requirement for the breakage of fibers in fiber reinforced PEEK.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The crack growth rate in the threshold region was found to increase with increase in load ratio (R) in carbon fiber reinforced PEEK. Fatigue Threshold on the other hand decreases with increase in load ratio.
2. A linear relationship was found to exist between Paris constant C and load ratio R. Similar relationship was found to exist between Paris exponent 'm' and R in this material.
3. There exists a linear relationship between $\log C$ and m in carbon fiber reinforced PEEK.
4. The crack growth mechanism in PEEK was found to be by the delamination in the fiber matrix interface region as well as fiber breakage in high ΔK region..

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DESIGN AND ANALYSIS
